

DEVELOPMENT STAGES OF MANAGEMENT IN THE TOURISM INDUSTRY

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Annotation: This article explores the fundamental concepts and principles of management, contemporary approaches to managing service organizations, and their unique characteristics in sociocultural services and tourism. It highlights the importance of decision-making in management and the information systems that support these decisions.

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуются фундаментальные концепции и принципы менеджмента, современные подходы к управлению обслуживающими организациями, их уникальные особенности в сфере социокультурных услуг и туризма. Это подчеркивает важность принятия решений в управлении и информационных систем, которые поддерживают эти решения.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola menejmentning asosiy tushunchalari va tamoyillarini, xizmat ko'rsatuvchi tashkilotlarni boshqarishning zamonaviy yondashuvlarini va ularning ijtimoiy-madaniy xizmatlar va turizmdagi o'ziga xos xususiyatlarini o'rganadi. U menejmentda qaror qabul qilishning muhimligini va bu qarorlarni qo'llab-quvvatlovchi axborot tizimlarini ta'kidlaydi.

Keywords: behavioral motivations, transit passengers, travelers, tourism expenses, interested clients.

Ключевые слова: поведенческие мотивы, транзитные пассажиры, путешественники, туристические расходы, заинтересованные клиенты.

Kalit so‘zlar: xatti-harakatlar motivlari, tranzit yo'lovchilar, sayohatchilar, turizm xarajatlari, manfaatdor mijozlar.

Management can be broadly defined as the art and science of achieving goals by effectively utilizing human labor, behavior, and intellect. It involves transforming unorganized elements into productive forces aimed at achieving specific objectives. Management can also be seen as a type of activity focused on overseeing organizational processes and managing people in various organizations. Referring to O. Bogdanov's formula for organizational processes, managing tourism can be understood as overseeing the interactions of its components: natural resources, labor, experience, intellect, and human behavior in the context of tourism as a field of human activity.

The essence of tourism management is tied to the specific characteristics that distinguish it from other areas. Although the term "tourism" is widely understood, it is essential to differentiate this form of human activity from others for scientific purposes. Key criteria include travel to places that are not a person's permanent residence, often involving experiences unrelated to their work, and the social relations and phenomena that arise from such travel.

Tourism is defined as the set of events and relationships occurring during individuals' leisure time spent away from home (for health, education, sports, cultural, and recreational purposes). The duration of the trip is a significant statistical measure. According to international standards, a maximum stay of one year qualifies as tourism, while Ukrainian law specifies six months. The distinction between a tourist and a traveler often relies on a minimum stay duration of 24 hours.

The economic aspect of tourism allows it to be viewed as an industry. The relationships formed within the "human-nature" system during the implementation of tourism activities are crucial in the context of the global economy's development.

Tourism activities contribute to restoring physical and mental well-being and developing individual abilities, taking place outside the individual's permanent residence. These activities directly impact health, social, cultural, and educational aspects of individuals' lives.

With the market economy's emergence in Uzbekistan coinciding with significant changes in global tourism, this sector has become one of the essential components of

the economy, providing jobs and opportunities for skill development. The rapid growth of employment in tourism exceeds that of other sectors. The development of both domestic and international tourism requires careful management.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan recognizes citizens' rights to leisure, yet various social issues (such as transportation, infrastructure, and food services) must be addressed to fully realize these rights. Effective tourism infrastructure management is therefore essential.

In implementing management in tourism, attention must focus on three key aspects: establishing standards and clear goals, evaluating results against expectations, and ensuring effective communication for decision-making. Reliable information is vital for making informed decisions, emphasizing the need for trustworthy communication channels.

In conclusion, the management of tourism organizations must adapt to ensure long-term reliability and competitiveness in the market. Development strategies should be tailored not only for individual organizations but also for the broader tourism sector.

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